

USE CASES

DATAMITE Use Cases (UCs) differentiate two key parts, **how organisations manage their data and how it is shared.**

In all UCs, **data governance, quality or security modules** are used, aiming at improving how data is managed within companies, how good is data, or interoperability.

DATA EXCHANGE WITHIN LARGE CORPORATIONS

○ CORPORATE MULTI-DOMAIN DATA EXCHANGE WITH EDIH SUPPORT

○ CORPORATE MULTI-SITE DATA EXCHANGE

ENERGY DATA SPACES

○ OFFERING DATA TO SERVICE PROVIDERS WITH DATASPACE

○ LEVERAGING ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION OPEN DATA

INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

○ CONNECTING EDWIN TO DATA MARKETS

○ CONNECTING MISTRAL TO THE EU AI-ON-DEMAND PLATFORM

ABOUT DATAMITE

- START DATE 01 JANUARY 2023
- DURATION 36 MONTHS
- OVERALL BUDGET €12M
- TOPIC HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-0104-Technologies and solutions for data trading, monetizing, exchange and interoperability (AI, Data and robotics Partnerships) (IA)

○ COORDINATED BY

THE TEAM

DATA

Monetization,
Interoperability,
Trading &
Exchange.

Unleashing
the Data
Monetisation
Potential

WWW
DATAMITE-HORIZON.EU

X
@DATAMITE_EU

IN
@DATAMITE

WHY DATAMITE

95%

of organisations suffer from the data decision gap, i.e., they cannot rely on data to make accurate decisions

10-30%

Poor-quality data alone is estimated to be costing companies around 10-30% of their revenue

60-73%

of data is never used for analytic and only 32% of companies can realize tangible and measurable value from data

MAIN RESULT

DATAMITE delivers a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework, to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training and business materials for European companies, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

BENEFITS OF DATAMITE

Improved Data Quality

Elevate your data's quality and adherence to FAIR principles, making it more reliable.

Revenue Generation

Keep control of your data while opening doors to new revenue streams.

Support for SMEs

DATAMITE's architecture aids in onboarding small and low-tech businesses into the data economy.

Skill Enhancement

Learn the technical and business skills needed to boost your data resources.

Connect with Stakeholders

Expand your opportunities to interact with partners in data markets, data spaces, and more.

DEVELOP

an open-source framework that enhances how companies manage and exchange data, boosting monetisation

CREATE

a Data Sharing module with tools for seamless data sharing and trading, focusing on data compatibility and control

SUPPLY

a set of open-source modules for data governance, quality, and security, that is easy to integrate into current systems

OUR OBJECTIVES

PUT DATAMITE INTO ACTION!

By testing its performance in six pilots and data-sharing scenarios

STRENGTHEN

European companies by providing models, indicators, and training resources for better data monetization

